

Data security, privacy and accessibility to support National and County Energy Planning in Kenya

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	Aim of this document	3
1.2	Background	3
1.2.1	Legal Framework	3
1.2.2	Data Governance	7
1.2.3	Governance Mechanisms	8
2	Methods.....	10
2.1	Data Repository	11
2.2	Stakeholder Engagement.....	12
2.3	Literature Review.....	13
3	Results.....	13
3.1	Roles and responsibilities	13
3.1.1	Discussion on roles and responsibilities.....	15
3.2	Data classification and metadata using CKAN	18
3.1.2	Discussion on data classification and metadata	18
3.2	Data lifecycle.....	20
3.2.1	Discussion on data lifecycle.....	21
4	Conclusion	21
	Bibliography	23
	Appendix	29

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of this document

This working paper reports on aspects related to data security and accessibility in connection with the analysis underpinning Integrated National Energy Plan (INEP) and the County Energy Plans (CEP) in Kenya. The aim is to identify and propose practical strategies to manage potential risks to data security and privacy and to ensure data is accessible to authorized users. This document introduces five key concepts of data governance and explores data privacy and security from the perspective of one of them. It then derives two governance mechanisms to manage data privacy and security based on several case studies drawn from stakeholder interactions at a series of workshops held in Kenya, and from experiences implementing a prototype data repository. The findings show how and where the data repository could be used to address data security issues and points out its benefits and drawbacks in the context of energy planning in Kenya.

1.2 Background

1.2.1 Legal Framework

It is a requirement for each county in Kenya to develop an energy plan following the framework proposed by the Ministry of Energy. This framework includes an assessment of the energy resources in the county, energy access indicators as well as energy efficiency measures among other topics (*Integrated National Energy Planning Framework*, 2021). Counties who started developing their CEPs have faced challenges that delay the production of this plan. One barrier, for example, is the lack of relevant data for energy planning and the inability to address data gaps for energy models due to poor data collection methods and low-quality datasets (Leonard et al., 2023a; Otieno et al., 2022). It has also been reported that some stakeholders within a county work in a siloed way and find it very challenging to share relevant data for the production of the CEP (Leonard et al., 2023b). Although there is a strong desire for data sharing, these stakeholders lack support, technology and mechanisms to do so (Leonard et al., 2023a).

In the context of energy planning, data sharing refers to the activities where two or more stakeholders exchange information used for energy models, analysis of an energy system or an assessment on gender equality and social inclusion issues connected to, for example, energy access and climate change resilience. The actors sharing data in this context include the national government, county governments, grid operators as well as the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation and the Energy (REREC) and Petroleum Regulatory Authority (EPRA) (Beltramo et al., 2024). These actors share data among each other with the purpose to develop the County Energy Plans (CEPs) and then Integrated National Energy Plan (INEP) in Kenya.

In terms of data sharing, various regulations and recommendations influence access to data as well as privacy and security in Kenya. At a continental level, there has been a push for the data revolution from the United Nations as well as the African Union. Together, these two bodies released the *African Data Consensus*, 2015 where they share a vision to strengthen statistics and promote data openness for sustainable development. At a national level, *The Constitution of Kenya*, 2010 states the right to privacy as well as the right to access to information. In this constitution, citizens are encouraged to participate actively in the public arena to ensure accountability and exercise of these rights. Active citizenship is also part of the *County Governments Act*, 2012 and is recognised as an enabler to access key information that shapes policy decision-making. The act also encourages and protects the rights of marginalised groups and minorities to access information. Building on these, the *Access to Information Act*, 2016 and the *Access to Information (General) Regulations*, 2021 were released. The purpose of the first one is to establish a framework for stakeholders to disclose information and provide it when requested, facilitating access to data for citizens and other relevant parties. On the other hand, the second document guides the processes for requesting data and proactive disclosure of information among other aspects related to data sharing. Both documents promote openness and play a key role in the context of energy planning in Kenya, as energy data should also be accessible.

These regulations have implications for data sharing and accessibility in Kenya's energy sector. The *Access to Information (General) Regulations*, 2021 require every organization holding data to appoint a designated individual responsible for handling data access requests. In the public sector, the chief executive officer takes this role, unless designated otherwise. This role involves receiving the request, retrieving the required information and granting access to the requester. It also requires the individual to seek the necessary approvals to share the information. The regulations also specify that any request needs to be completed within 21 days of the submission, with an additional 14 days if the request is extensive or requires consultations.

Therefore, when defining a data requesting process within an organization the role of the chief executive officer must be considered since it plays a key role in the requesting process. However, the organization still has the freedom to define how to handle the process internally and include approvals or data transformation necessary to comply with other privacy issues such as protecting personal identities, intellectual property or matters of national security (*Access to Information Act*, 2016). Other aspects related to the data lifecycle influenced by these policies are the storage and the possibility of appealing the decision if the request to access data is denied. In Kenya, personal data must be processed through a server and data centre located in the country (*Data Protection Act*, 2019)

In terms of data privacy and security, the *Data Protection Act*, 2019 became the first data law in the country focused on managing and sharing personal data. This act was inspired by the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and shares some similarities in terms of practices and semantics. In the context of energy planning, the INEP framework requires counties in Kenya to

include cross-cutting issues which require inputs from personal data and fall into the Data Protection Act (*Integrated National Energy Planning Framework, 2021*). The Data Protection Act, *THE DATA PROTECTION (REGISTRATION OF DATA CONTROLLERS AND DATA PROCESSORS) REGULATIONS, 2021* and *The Data Protection General Regulations, 2021* serve as a guide to managing personal data specifying how it should be processed, retained and stored.

Some practices to comply with the Data Protection Act include requesting the data subject for their consent to use their information and the possibility of the data subject to request for anonymisation and pseudonymisation of their information. It seems like each organisation has the freedom to choose the internal procedure to handle these requests, and it is the responsibility of either the data controller or the data processor to handle them.

Box 1. The Data Protection Act, 2019

- Data controller: natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purpose and means of processing of personal data.
- Data processor: natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the data controller.

Finally, in terms of energy data, the *Energy Act, 2019* states that in the relationship between a licensing authority and licensee, the latter must provide information in the form and manner required by the licensing authority. This information can be shared among officers and authorities concerning energy and other stakeholders but not with other third parties without prior consent in writing (*Energy Act, 2019*). One example of a licensee is the Independent Power Producers (IPPs) of energy who, if requested, would need to provide data to the Energy and Petroleum Regulatory Authority (EPRA) under this act.

Box 2. Energy Act, 2019

- Licence: Any document or instrument in writing granted under the Energy Act, 2019, to any person or authorizing the importation, exportation, generation, transmission, distribution and supply of electrical energy or the exploration and production geothermal energy, in the manner described in such document of instrument.
- Licensee: Holder of any licence issued under the Energy Act, 2019
- Licensing authority: Any person or body, including the Authority, with power to grant, revoke or suspend a licence under the Energy Act, 2019
- Authority: Energy and Petroleum Regulatory Authority

Other relevant data practices not established in the acts but influenced by them include security checks to determine who is the person accessing the information, and different protocols depending on the type of organization trying to retrieve information. Whether it is a citizen, another public organization in Kenya, the private sector or an NGO in the country different processes could be implemented to protect data privacy. This segregation of processes by sector becomes relevant

when information wants to be shared outside of the country, as the acts have more strict protocols to ensure privacy and confidentiality.

While the acts are in place, significant work remains to ensure their full implementation. The Open Institute reported that there are asymmetries between the counties on the adoption of these acts, for example, while some have implemented data protection or information officers, in other counties these functions remain scattered across various officials (*A Study of National and (Sub) National Data Practices in Kenya*, 2021). Beltramo et al. (2024) describes various efforts to develop open portals to share governmental data such as the Kenyan Open Data Initiative or the Kenya Data Portal. The first one was a consequence of the Constitutional Right of access to information, but it is currently inoperable. The second portal provides access to a limited selection of national statistical information generated by Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS), and it does not include data from the energy sector.

The legal framework defines key concepts used for data security and privacy in the Kenyan context. These concepts are shown in Box 3, including anonymisation and differential privacy. All of these will be discussed further in section 3.3.

Box 3. Data security definitions

- Personal data: any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (*Data Protection Act*, 2019).
- Identifiable natural person: a person who can be identified directly or indirectly, by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social or social identity (*Data Protection Act*, 2019).
- Profiling: means any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person's race, sex, pregnancy, marital status, health status, ethnic social origin, colour, age, disability, religion, conscience, belief, culture, dress, language or birth; personal preferences, interests, behaviour, location or movements (*Data Protection Act*, 2019).
- Pseudonymisation: means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, and such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data is not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person (*Data Protection Act*, 2019).
- Anonymisation: to remove identifying information from (something, such as computer data) so that the original source cannot be known (Jamul, 2023).
- Differential privacy: rigorous and scientific definition of privacy-sensitive information release—that defines a limit or bounds on the amount of privacy loss you can have when you release information (Jamul, 2023).

1.2.2 Data Governance

Data governance is the exercise of managing data assets through decision-making rights and duties, and the implementation of standards, policies, procedures, roles, and responsibilities within a data community (Alhassan et al., 2016; Ladley 2020; Eryurek 2021). A data community is a group of stakeholders who share a social, economic or professional interest across the data lifecycle to create and manage knowledge resources (*African Data Consensus*, 2015; Nishikawa, 2020).

There are a variety of data governance models that are tailored to the specific needs of communities. For example, data can be shared using a data sharing pool model where the purpose is to generate profit or it can be shared using a data cooperative model to empower data subjects (Micheli et al., 2020). Depending on the nature and purpose of the model, data can be stored in one or multiple data repositories and use other software to support governance activities.

In the context of energy planning in Kenya, we are using a framework including six different data domains to understand data governance. This is a similar approach used by Khatri & Brown (2010); including roles and responsibilities and data monitoring as described by Abraham et al. (2019). Figure 1 shows the data domains and Box 4 provides details on the different aspects of each.

Box 4. Data domain definitions

- Data principles: Normative, reusable and directive set of statements that describe the basic doctrines of data governance. (Brous et al., 2016; *The TOGAF® Standard, Version 9.2*, n.d.)
- Data Lifecycle: Simple series of standardized, documented, and repeatable tasks used to govern data. (Abraham et al., 2019; *What Is a Workflow?*, 2021)
- Data quality: Ability of data to satisfy its usage requirements across any stage in its life cycle. (Abraham et al., 2019; Moses et al., 2022)
- Data privacy and security: Preservation of security concerning access, use, processing, and storage controls. (Abraham et al., 2019; Jamul, 2023)
- Data monitoring: Tracking and enforcing conformance with regulatory requirements and organizational policies, standards, procedures, and SLAs. (Abraham et al., 2019)

Figure 1. Data domains – Data governance framework for energy planning in Kenya

While these domains are represented in separate boxes, they overlap in different characteristics. For example, when evaluating the *data lifecycle*, aspects of *data privacy and security* need to be discussed when data is archived, erased or deleted. These processes in the lifecycle need to closely follow the protocols established by the data privacy and security domain, to prevent data breaches and maintain privacy.

In this working paper, we will be reporting only on the data lifecycle domain as this has been explored in the context of energy data sharing in Kenya. However, data security is relevant for all data domains and will be explored in future stages of the research.

A data lifecycle is the high-level representation of the phases involved in the management of data (Shah et al., 2021). The analysis of a data lifecycle can vary depending on the framework used (Ding et al., 2012; IBM, 2024; International, 2017). In this context, we find it relevant to follow the framework used by Shah et al., 2021 including the activities described in box 5.

Box 5. Data Lifecycle Framework for data-driven governments (Shah et al., 2021)

- Planning (optional): Illustrates activities to be performed in the medium and long terms during the data lifecycle.
- Collection (mandatory): Set of activities through which data is gathered from different sources and in different formats.
- Preparation (mandatory): Data integration, filtering and enrichment.
- Analysis (mandatory): Developing data analysis to extract knowledge and discover new insights
- Visualization (optional): Presentation and visualization of the outcomes.
- Access (optional): Ways of communication between the data provider and data consumer.
- Share/Publish (mandatory): Determine what data can and should be shared and published with appropriate security measures
- Use, re(use) & feedback (mandatory): Discovering new and valuable information from datasets and provide feedback.
- Archive (optional): Keeping a record for obsolete data
- End of life (optional): Duplicated and useless data is removed from the system
- Storage (performed throughout the lifecycle): Save data securely

1.2.3 Governance Mechanisms

Governance mechanisms are the means that help actors plan and control data management activities (Abraham et al., 2019). We have identified three governance mechanisms relevant for the management of data in the context of energy planning in Kenya. *Roles and responsibilities* refers to the activity of assigning privileges and tasks to users, groups, public, or other roles (Roles, 2024). An initial assessment of distinct data governance models led us to this first definition of roles and responsibilities in a data community as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Data community roles and responsibilities

Data Ecosystem		
Data Community		
Data governance council	Define direction of the data governance Monitor overall data governance and data governance projects Resolve conflicts	(Abraham et al., 2019; Informatica, n.d.)
Data producer/provider/owner	Collect and produce data Aggregate data Define data risks Define data requirements	(Abraham et al., 2019; Lis & Otto, 2021)
Data consumer/ Data requester	Use data for analysis Define data requirements Monitor data issues	(Abraham et al., 2019)

Previous work in the UK PACT Project in Kenya focused on mapping the data flows. To expand on this work, we integrate the roles described in Table 1 with a visual representation of the data flows presented as presented in Figure 2 using the concepts of data ecosystem and data community proposed in the *African Data Consensus*, 2015. Details on the definitions of each term are presented in Box 6.

Figure 2. Data ecosystem diagram.

Box 6. Data community definitions

- Data ecosystem: Multiple data communities, all types of data, institutions, laws and policy frameworks and innovative technologies and tools interacting to share information (*African Data Consensus*, 2015)
- Data community: Group of stakeholders who share a social, economic or professional interest across the data lifecycle to create and manage knowledge resources (*African Data Consensus*, 2015; Nishikawa, 2020)
- Data provider: Actor that collects, creates and/or aggregates data, defines data risks and data requirements. (Abraham et al., 2019; Lis & Otto, 2021).
- Data consumer: Actor that uses data for analysis, defines data requirements and monitors data issues (Abraham et al., 2019).
- Data intermediary: Third-party actors who provide specialized resources and capabilities to (i) enhance the supply, flow, and/or use of open data and/or (ii) strengthen the relationships among various open data stakeholders (Massey, 2022)
- Member: Actor that produces and consumes data or participates in the management of data in the data community.

Data classification is a mechanism where data is ranked according to the risks associated with it. Some of the benefits of this mechanism include, understanding how data used, continuous alignment with data protection law and the ability to tailor data protection tools (Bhajaria, 2022). Data classification allows organizations to determine the value of their data allowing them to manage it in ways that reflect that value (Simorjay, 2014). Examples of data classification include defining data as commercially sensitive - which means the data is used to generate an economic benefit (Hirth, 2020)- or as personal data, defined in Box 3.

Another relevant mechanism used together with data classification is metadata. *Metadata* is used describe sensitivity levels as well as any other relevant information related to a dataset (Abraham et al., 2019). In the next sections we describe the methods used in this paper and suggest how these mechanisms can be used together with CKAN to improve data governance in the context of energy planning in Kenya.

2 Methods

To assess strategies to manage the potential risks to data security and privacy and to ensure data is accessible to authorised users, we combined three main methods. In section 2.1, we describe how we implemented a prototype data repository in partnership with stakeholders to explore different strategies for managing data using one (or many potential) tools. In section 2.2, we describe the overall approach to stakeholder engagement, conducted in person and remotely across workshops and numerous other group and bilateral interactions. Finally, in section 2.3, we describe the approach used for the literature review.

2.1 Data Repository

A data repository is a digital or physical environment where data is stored, organised, managed, accessed and preserved for a period to be used for analytical or reporting purposes (*Data Repository - Glossary - Open Raven, n.d.; Research Data Management Glossary, n.d.; What Is a Data Repository, n.d.*). For this project, we reviewed a shortlist of 4 tools and finally identified CKAN as the most suitable for the management of energy data in Kenya. We drew upon the World Bank Open Data Toolkit (*Open Data Toolkit |Technology Options | Data, n.d.*) and shortlisted CKAN, InvenioRDM, Semantic Media Wiki and Socrata for further review. CKAN is an open-source data management system that enables actors to easily publish, share and work with data. It enables users to catalogue, store and access datasets using a graphical user interface (*CKAN - The Open Source Data Management System, 2024*).

CKAN provides a diverse set of tools used to maintain data security and privacy. From the software side, the system has inbuilt alerts used to identify vulnerable dependencies of the code (*About Dependabot Alerts, 2024*) or any other security vulnerability (*Security Feature Detail Page, 2024*). From the user interface side, CKAN provides user authentication through the use of usernames and passwords, tags, organisations, roles, and private and public datasets. If required, it also provides a security extension that includes stronger password reset tokens, brute force protection, two-factor authentication and more (*Data-Govt-Nz/Ckanext-Security, 2017/2024*).

Organisations and roles are used in CKAN to manage data security and access to datasets. Box 7 defines the different CKAN roles assigned to users for the management of data within their organisation. This set of roles enables data sharing within an organisation. Users can define private and public data sets, while public data sets can be seen by any user with access to the platform, private data sets can only be accessed by users in the same organisation (*Organizations and Authorization — CKAN 2.11.1 Documentation, n.d.*). In CKAN v2.9 developers introduced the concept of a collaborator to allow data-set level authorization. Administrators can restrict access to a single dataset between two organisations. Other features include creating datasets without an account or creating datasets not owned by an organisation. (*Configuration Options — CKAN 2.11.1 Documentation, n.d.*).

Box 7. CKAN organization roles (*User Guide — CKAN 2.11.1 Documentation, n.d.*)

- Member – can see the organization’s private datasets
- Editor – can edit and publish datasets
- Admin – can add, remove and change roles for organization members
- Collaborator – can access one private dataset from an organization they are not part of (*Organizations and Authorization — CKAN 2.11.1 Documentation, n.d.*)

CKAN implements a metadata framework. Box 8 describes the metadata fields used in CKAN when uploading a dataset in the environment. The platform allows for customization and users can add up to three metadata fields defined by the organization.

Box 8. Metadata used CKAN (*Metadata Feature Detail Page, n.d.*)

Field	Description
Title	Allows intuitive labelling of the dataset for search, sharing and linking.
Unique identifier	Dataset has a unique URL which is customizable by the publisher.
Description	Additional information describing or analysing the data. This can either be static or an editable wiki which anyone can contribute to instantly or via admin moderation.
Tags	See what labels the dataset in question belongs to. Tags also allow for browsing between similarly tagged datasets in addition to enabling better discoverability through tag search and faceting by tags.
License	Instant view of whether the data is available under an open licence or not. This makes it clear to users whether they have the rights to use, change and re-distribute the data.
Custom Field (extra fields)	These hold any additional information, such as location data (see geospatial feature) or types relevant to the publisher or dataset. How and where extra fields display is customizable.
Revision history	CKAN allows you to display a revision history for datasets which are freely editable by users (as is thedatahub.org)
Visibility	Allows private and public datasets
Source	URL to link to the source
Version	Allows for a versions record
Author	Define the author of the dataset
Author Email	
Maintainer	Define the responsible person of maintaining the dataset
Maintainer Email	

The prototype data repository used during the project is hosted on Microsoft Azure until the end of March 2025, after which it will be taken offline. The source code for deploying the prototype instance is available on GitHub, https://github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/ccg_ckan and the prototype, while live, is available online at <http://kenya.swedencentral.cloudapp.azure.com/>

2.2 Stakeholder Engagement

Engagement with stakeholders involved two workshops and continuous follow-up activities with the county governments. The first workshop, *Data governance framework for energy data in Kenya: Prototyping a data repository framework to support INEP* (hereafter referred to as Workshop 1) was held on June 25th, 2024, in Kenya. The session aimed to map data acquisition workflows using three different data sharing scenarios: (i) national to county level (top-down), (ii) across county

departments (horizontal) and (iii) county to national level (bottom-up). Participants took part in two exercises where proposed improvements to the existing processes were discussed.

The second workshop (Workshop 2), *Data Governance Framework and repository for energy data in Kenya* took place on October 1st, 2024, and focused on using and evaluating the CKAN platform. The activities in this workshop included logging into the platform, conducting searches, adding organizations, uploading private datasets and adding collaborators.

Representatives from county governments and national stakeholders attended both workshops, including the Council of Governors, the Ministry of Energy and Petroleum (MoE) and the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS). More details on Workshop 1 and Workshop 2 can be found Ramirez & Tembo (2025).

Following these workshops, we maintained engagement with county governments through follow-up calls, including Kilifi, Meru, Nakuru and Tana River County. These additional sessions aimed to provide additional training on the CKAN platform and to gather feedback on the diverse features of the software.

2.3 Literature Review

Our approach for the literature review comprised a keyword-based search for published papers as well as relevant grey literature. The initial search terms used were “data governance model”, “data commons” and “data governance framework” including “energy sector”, “Africa” or “low-middle income countries” when deemed relevant. Grey literature included Kenyan law in reference to data sharing and reports from organizations that worked with data governance and data flows in Kenya including The Open Institute and Climate Compatible Growth (CCG).

3 Results

In this section we explore data security and privacy issues relevant for energy planning in Kenya across the data lifecycle domain and three governance mechanisms (roles and responsibilities, metadata, data classification) These insights have evolved out of interactions with stakeholders and literature on the topic. We identify data privacy and security risks and propose measures to prevent data leakages and increase data security. At the same time, we also explore the data repository as a tool to increase accessibility in this context.

3.1 Roles and responsibilities

To understand roles and responsibilities in Kenya’s energy data community we applied the concept of the data ecosystem introduced in Figure 2. The main objective of the energy data community studied in this report is the production of the integrated national energy plan (INEP).

Figure 3. Energy data ecosystem in Kenya.

The result of the analysis is shown in Figure 3. The two circles represent the two main data communities. We identified one energy planning community that focuses on data for energy planning both at a county and a national level. The actors in this community include national government departments such as KNBS and MoE; parastatals such as Kenya Power and Lightning Company (KPLC) and Kenya Electricity Generating Company (KenGen); and county government departments. The Ministry of Energy acts as an approver meaning that in some processes, they deal with requests for data from a data consumer. The county energy planning committees (CEPCs) and the integrated national energy planning committee (INEPC) collect data from these institutions and play a central role in the community as they develop the energy plans.

In the energy planning community, the actors involved are classified as data providers, data consumers or members. Data providers only include KNBS, while data consumers only include the INEPC. On the other hand, members include county departments, KPLC, CEPCs, KenGen, the Geothermal Development Company (GDC), the Nuclear Power and Energy Agency (NuPEA), Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO), the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation (REREC) and Energy and Petroleum Regulatory Authority (EPRA).

A second community includes other stakeholders that consume or provide energy data but are not involved in data management, for examples NGOs present in Kenya. Other stakeholders include

citizens, universities in Kenya, and organizations outside Kenya who request information from any of the actors within the energy data community. While this second community is also complex, it does not fall into the scope of this working paper and therefore it is presented in simple terms by just describing a data flow from this community to the energy data community.

In the background of the diagram, the legal frameworks, discussed in section 1.2.1, are listed as they provide the broad regulatory context influencing all data activities. These frameworks establish guidelines for protecting sensitive data and sharing information influencing activities between stakeholders in the energy data community as well as activities between both communities identified in this ecosystem.

During the workshops, we also discussed issues related to roles and responsibilities. In Workshop 1, one county representative mentioned that sharing water-related datasets would always require approval from the water department. Therefore, it was challenging for them to determine where the repository could be in the data acquisition workflow since this approval is required. During Workshop 2, the participants uploaded private datasets to the CKAN platform and used the built-in roles described in Box 7. All participants were able to upload a private dataset; however, adding collaborators to a dataset was a more challenging task that some participants were not able to complete.

3.1.1 Discussion on roles and responsibilities

Figure 3 highlights the absence of a data intermediary to facilitate data sharing in the community, and the absence of the data governance council to coordinate data management. Since none of these roles are formally established, the governance of data in Kenya is informal and less standardized than it could be. This poses a risk when sharing data, as protocols and processes vary between each organization. Without standardization, some processes may be insufficient while others are overly strict. It has been reported that a data repository in Kenya, including protocols for its use, could benefit data-sharing activities (Leonard et al., 2023a). Therefore, having a data intermediary together with data security procedures could reduce risks and protect data privacy.

Since a data intermediary could benefit data practices in Kenya, it is relevant to consider how the structure of the community would be with such entity and which organization(s) could take on that role. (Leonard et al., 2023b) reported that stakeholders are interested in using a data repository to share information with the possibility that the MoE or Kenya Power could host it. While there is a desire to have this repository, there is still a tension regarding who should be the host.

Figure 4. Data intermediary in the energy data ecosystem in Kenya.

Figure 4 illustrates the scenario where the MoE acts as a data intermediary and how the data flows could look like. Similarly to Figure 3, there are two data communities including the energy planning data community and the same stakeholders retain their roles except for the MoE. Since the MoE acts as an intermediary, all data flows go across the organization with the exception of the CEPCs flow to the INEPC, which only represents how county energy plans (CEPs) are used to create the INEP.

Implementing a data repository and having the MoE as a data intermediary could benefit data governance in Kenya since data flows would be centralized and all processes would be facilitated by this institution. Additionally, the approvals needed from the MoE in the data acquisition off different national organizations would be more efficient and handled according to established protocols. However, this could create power imbalances between MoE and the other institutions as the technical needs from the data repository would be handled by MoE granting them all the privileges of the platform at a user and administrator level. This also means that the MoE would have more technical responsibilities and incur costs of hosting in the data ecosystem.

These drawbacks could be mitigated by using a model that delegates these responsibilities to other stakeholders and grants agency to them to make decisions. This approach could be addressed by creating a data governance council integrated by users in the data community as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Data governance council in the energy data ecosystem in Kenya.

The reason why the INEPC and the CEPCs could be a data governance council is because they are integrated by multiple actors from the organizations of the energy planning data community. Therefore, each organization would have influence in the governance of data and agency on its management. One potential drawback is the contribution of multiple stakeholders, which could lead to inefficiencies in decision-making processes. This issue might be addressed by limiting the number of stakeholders within INEPC and CEPCs to handle data aspects. The data community is yet to provide feedback for this scenario to determine whether it is a possibility or not.

In our research, we have reflected on how to define these roles using CKAN. In the first place, the use of CKAN organizations limits data sharing as any user with access to an organization can view all data sets. Therefore, the use of CKAN collaborators is key to ensure data security during the data sharing process. Participants of Workshop 2 found it challenging to add collaborators. Thus, it is important to identify the barriers for completing the task and assess the training needs for the counties to develop an effective solution.

In the data sharing processes of KNBS and KPLC, the MoE is involved as an approver. Within CKAN, we have not identified a mechanism to implement approver roles. This poses a risk as the organizations will not be able to automate these processes using the platform and will not have a registry of the approval process. In this complex system, it seems that approvals happen quite often and while they ensure sensitive data is not shared unintentionally, they make the processes bureaucratic. While some freedom to define these processes is positive, standardization could

improve data mapping and documentation efforts, reduce processes complexity and maintenance. This idea will be further explored in the next section, reflecting on how to standardize data acquisition approvals depending on the sensitivity of the data.

3.2. Data classification and metadata using CKAN

In the context of energy data in Kenya we have identified that commercially sensitive data and personal data is used for energy planning. Commercially sensitive data includes information on the accessibility to specific resources like wood supply, agricultural residues, the potential of solar power, location and capacity for geothermal power generation, wind power generation potential and location, and electricity sales, among others (*Integrated National Energy Planning Framework, 2021*). For example, during a follow-up call, county stakeholders highlighted the commercial sensitivity of water datasets. This dataset has attributes that make it sensitive, but it can be shared with specific stakeholders if some attributes are removed, e.g. the data is transformed. We identified three different scenarios where this type of data can be shared: within the department where it is accessible to the employees with all its attributes, shared with NGOs where some attributes are removed, and to the public where also more attributes are removed.

In terms of personal data, energy planning considers crosscutting issues related to gender, innovation, research, environment, climate change, health and safety (*Integrated National Energy Planning Framework, 2021*). For example, for the *County Energy Plan Nakuru, 2021*, a survey was used to collect data including gender, age, education level, income, cooking behaviour, electricity use and behaviour, gas use in the household, and paraffin use to understand energy demand. While personal data is collected for energy planning, we did not identify, during our stakeholder interaction, any case where personal data privacy was compromised.

During Workshop 2 and follow-up interviews, we tested the metadata used in CKAN presented in Box 8. We concluded that these fields are relevant for stakeholders; however, questions were raised about their definitions and usage. Specifically, stakeholders during the follow-up interviews questioned the distinction between "author" and "maintainer" and how these roles should be defined. Additionally, they asked about the different types of licenses and their appropriate use. Both issues were also discussed in meetings with UK PACT partners, who found it unclear how to populate these fields or choose suitable licenses.

3.1.2 Discussion on data classification and metadata

The risks of sharing commercially sensitive data in the energy sector include the possibility of data leakage that can generate economic losses (Wang et al., 2023). In relation to these data, it remains unclear whether the datasets used for energy planning have the possibility to be shared and under which conditions. It also remains unclear which datasets that describe resource availability are considered commercially sensitive by the stakeholders and under which conditions they can be

shared, or, in other words, which attributes need to be removed. Defining and documenting these characteristics is key, but it can become a very extensive job with a high level of maintenance.

When it comes to personal data, the *Data Protection Act, 2019* suggests using anonymization and pseudonymisation (Box 3) to prevent a person from being identified. While these methods provide an amount of protection, there is still a risk an individual is identified using other publicly available data sets (Jamul, 2023). There is currently a low risk of re-identification in Kenya when these methods are used. However, in case datasets with this information are made public or open, we recommend using differential privacy.

When using personal data to analyse groups rather than individuals, profiling is an important aspect to consider (Box 3). In the context of energy planning and survey data profiling can lead to inferences about the behaviour of certain groups in terms of energy use, types of fuels consumed, and potential risks they might face. For instance, in *Makueni County Energy Plan 2023-2032, 2021* it is discussed how “traditional gender roles expose women to indoor pollution from firewood use [...]”. This statement highlights gender inequalities and demonstrates how such data can be used to conclude on social issues. While this example is not negative, it illustrates how this data can be used to create narratives. If this data is not adequately protected, there is a risk of profiling that reinforces biased perspectives on a group, facing issues like de-individualisation – judging individuals based on group rather than individual characteristics or merits-, discrimination or stereotyping (Schermer, 2013).

Another issue with sharing personal data is the risk of taking data out of context. Abebe et al. (2021) discuss how historically marginalized groups can potentially be harmed by sharing their personal data due to power imbalances and the risk of data misinterpretation. In this regard, data sovereignty emphasizes the need for diverse data groups and communities to reclaim ownership of their data and incorporate their cultural values into analyses (Walter, 2021; Walter & Suina, 2019). In the context of energy planning, there is a risk that certain groups may not be fairly represented, that power asymmetries may persist, and that data may be misinterpreted or decontextualized. Including vulnerable groups in these discussions is crucial, though it remains a significant challenge.

One way we have identified to maintain privacy and security in datasets is using CKAN tags and other relevant metadata, making datasets easier to find while also describing the associated risks. For instance, stakeholders in our previous example highlighted three distinct scenarios that could be categorized using tags such as *private* datasets for departmental use, *NGOs* for data shared with fewer attributes for NGO use, and *public* for non-sensitive data that can be shared with any individual or organization.

Since some metadata fields confuse participants, it is necessary to clearly define how metadata will be used in this context. The definition of licenses and author/maintainer is relevant for data sharing and therefore we believe it is important to provide clear guidance on their application.

3.2 Data lifecycle

During Workshop 1, stakeholders defined data acquisition workflows across three distinct levels including national to county level, across county departments and from county level to national level. We concluded that there are processes in place for sharing energy data in the three levels examined that are very bureaucratic and time consuming. Figure 6 shows the resulting diagrams defined by the groups of county and national actors. These workflows are based on hypothetical scenarios involving specific county departments and national-level stakeholders.

Figure 6. Energy data acquisition workflows in Kenya

In terms of data privacy and security, we believe the processes have sufficient approvals to reduce the risk of sharing sensitive information. Particularly the county to national scenario is more complex, requiring a considerable number of approvals within the county. This practice benefits data privacy and security, but it also slows down information sharing and limits access to data. All the data-sharing processes involve the Chief Officer in the organization where the data is being requested, which complies with the Access to Information Act.

During the follow-up interviews it has become more evident that there is awareness of the risks associated with data sharing and that data is classified according to these risks. However, there are no processes defined for how to share information by *dataset type* and instead a more cautious approach dominates data-sharing activities. There is a need to further investigate whether this approach has to do with a strict strategy to data security, insufficient knowledge on privacy

protection or to avoid commercial risks. Finding the right balance between openness and data security remains a key challenge.

3.2.1 Discussion on data lifecycle

We identified risks in the data sharing processes across the three levels we explored: processes they are not documented and are not automated. Actors attempting to access datasets for the first time might struggle to understand how to acquire data, delaying their work. It remains a challenge to determine whether data is shared according to the defined workflows, and there is a risk that some datasets are shared without proper checks. Therefore, these processes are not transparent, and accountability is not possible.

Moreover, according to the Access to Information Act, the Chief Officer has the responsibility to collect the information requested and to grant or reject access to the dataset. However, this act does not specify whether other approvals are necessary. This suggests that data acquisition in the three levels explored could be reduced by allowing direct requests to the Chief Officer. The Chief Officer then could seek for internal approvals and share the dataset directly with the requester. To help ease data acquisition we recommend complementing data classification with the development of tailored acquisition workflows for each data type.

The risks and barriers for data acquisition can be mitigated by using CKAN. Users in the platform can add, edit and delete datasets (*User Guide — CKAN 2.11.1 Documentation*, n.d.), keeping track of the changes and increasing transparency. CKAN also tracks access to data which benefits accountability.

However, incorporating approval processes remains a challenge. While approvals could be automated and integrated in the workflow, developing such a feature may be necessary within the current CKAN environment. Now, it seems more likely to maintain the approval process manually to make them more efficient in the future by documenting and reducing the number of steps in the approval process.

4 Conclusion

This working paper identifies data privacy and security risks in energy planning in Kenya and proposes practical strategies to manage these to ensure data access to authorised users. By focusing on data risks, data practices and the use of a data repository, the analysis suggests actionable recommendations to support the development of the INEP and the CEPs.

Primarily, the risks identified include sharing data with unauthorized users including confidential information with commercial value and personal data that makes it possible to identify an individual. While Kenya's current cautious approach to data acquisition reduces these risks, it also delays energy planning and limits data availability. Insufficient documentation and a lack of

standardized processes further reduce transparency and increases the risk of inconsistent data handling.

To manage these risks, we propose the adoption of data classification. This will allow a more thorough definition of data acquisition processes including workflows per data type following the defined classification. This approach will facilitate a transition from the cautious approach to an approach based on defined protocols and criteria for data sharing. When sharing personal data, anonymization and pseudonymization remain effective practices that follow Kenya's Data Protection Act. In the future, when open data initiatives are implemented, differential privacy should be considered to protect data.

The prototype data repository, built on CKAN, provides features that help implement these data security protocols. First, it offers built-in components such as roles and permissions which help control, register and follow access to sensitive data. The metadata framework allows users to define the data owner and contact points, as well as the use of tags for data classification purposes. The collaborator feature is important for sharing data across organisations and should be enabled in the environment. Some other benefits include the ability of stakeholders to effectively use the platform, however, training is required to address knowledge gaps. One key drawback is that CKAN does not enable approval processes and therefore this would need to remain manual without explicit development effort.

Finally, the data repository could be hosted by the MoE acting as a data intermediary. This should be supported by the creation of a data governance council involving actors in the data community. Actors in the INEPC and CEPCs could take this responsibility, however this remains to be explored. Future work includes the definition of data security protocols and processes, the definition of tags with stakeholder feedback, the definition of workflows per data type and exploring other data domains and their intersection with data security and privacy.

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